

Remote Patient Health Monitoring using IoT

Dr. P. W. Raut, Ishwari Chandrayan, Rishika Jain, Ritika Potturi, Aishwarya Ujjainkar, Pratiksha Sawale
Department of Electronics and Telecommunication Engineering,
Yeshwantrao Chavan College of Engineering,
Nagpur, Maharashtra, India

Abstract:- The motive of our project is to measure two parameters of patient. We have measured body temperature and heart rate using arduino and GSM module. Heart rate can be measured using pulse sensor and body temperature can be measured using LM35 sensor. The pulse sensor is basically used to show the readings in BPM (Beat Per Minute) and the body temperature will be displayed on the connected LCD along with BPM readings. And the displayed output will be sent to the registered mobile number using GSM module. With the implementation of this project we can measure body temperature and heart rate using GSM module and arduino and send the output to the registered mobile number of doctor by indicating whether the temperature and BPM is high, normal or low.

Keywords:- Pulse Sensor, Arduino, LM 35 Sensor, LCD Display, GSM Module.

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's world, now-a-days the maximum use of resources is always beneficial. So, the use of wireless technology is important to meet the need of remote control and monitoring. Remote patient health monitoring using Iot is a technology which helps us to monitor patients health even when the patient is not in the hospital or clinic. This device basically saves time of both patient and doctor and hence helps in increasing efficiency of health services.

The human health is one of the most important concern in the world. Everything becomes meaningless when one falls sick and dies due to improper medical. If we take early precautions on time then lots of patients can be saved. Among human health body temperature and heart rate plays the major role. In the medical field, the patients in the wards are usually the patients who need critical care due to acute, life-threatening illness or injury this device will be very helpful. The system efficiently updates doctor about health of patients as well as accurately calculates the heart rate and temperature of patient.

II. COMPONENT SPECIFICATIONS

The system consists of the sensors, whose individual specifications are mentioned below:

A. Pulse sensor

[1]Pulse sensor is a uncomplicated sensor which has many applications. It is made up of three pins : Vcc ,ground and the input signal. The led which is present at the center of the pulse sensor is basically used to detect heartbeat. The nature of this sensor is a heart shape. The advantage of using this sensor is that there is a noise elimination circuit below

the led which will help to keep away the surrounding noise from affecting the readings. When we connect a pulse sensor with Arduino or GSM Module the LED which is present on the center of the pulse sensor will be turned ON. The pulse sensor will only work when the Vcc is connected in 3v or 5v with the help of any internet connection.

Fig. 1: Pulse sensor

B. Arduino

Fig. 2: ARDUINO UNO

[6]The Arduino Uno is nothing but a microcontroller board based on the microchip ATmega328 and is developed by arduino.cc .The board is made up of 14 digital pins, 6

Fig. 5: Block diagram of the system

V. OUTCOMES

- The person will come to know about their heart rate in BPM (Beats Per Minute) by placing the finger in the pulse sensor and will get to know whether their heart beat is low, normal or high.
- When the LED will glow it will indicate that circuit is working properly and in this project we have used a LM35 temperature sensor which displays the body temperature on the LCD connected to it.
- This system describes the working of a very low cost remote patient health monitoring system which reads heart rate and body temperature and updates the report of the measured value as a text message to the doctor.
- This helps the people who are in remote areas and old people who has to visit the hospital on daily bases to check bpm and temperature.

VI. CONCLUSION

This device is established for home use by patients that are not in a life-threatening situation but need to be timely observed by doctor or family. So that we can effortlessly protect many lives by providing them speedy services. As per our title, remote patient health monitoring using Iot design is based on research idea that meets the patient's needs. The advantage of using this system is that it is very easy to use and handle individually. Also it take less than 1 minute for getting the exact result and sends the observed result to the doctor using GSM module.

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